

FOSTERING CREATIVE THINKING IN CHILDREN THROUGH AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article outlines the elements of integration, the integrative approach, and the benefits of using this approach to enhance creative thinking in primary school students.*

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Enhancing creative thinking in children is a vital aspect of primary education. Utilizing an integrative approach, which merges various educational strategies and subjects, can greatly boost the development of creative thinking skills in young learners. This method involves combining different disciplines and teaching techniques to create an engaging and comprehensive learning environment that promotes critical thinking, innovative problem-solving, and creative expression.

Understanding Creative Thinking: Creative thinking encompasses the ability to generate original and inventive ideas, solve problems in unique ways, and think outside the box. It includes:

- Divergent Thinking: Generating a wide range of ideas and solutions.
- Convergent Thinking: Narrowing down ideas to identify the most effective solution.
- Critical Thinking: Assessing and refining ideas to improve them.

Building these skills in primary education is essential as they form the basis for future success both academically and personally.

According to Yu.M. Kolyagin, integration in the education system can be used in two different ways:

1. Forming a whole, integrated vision of the world around us in students (where integration is considered as an educational goal).
2. Finding a common platform for converging the knowledge provided by subjects (here it is an integration-educational tool).

In integration by the first meaning, as soon as the student takes the first step in the field of knowledge, he imagines the world as a single whole, where all its elements are interconnected.

In the second sense, integration should be able to realize new ideas at the point of mutual collision of knowledge from academic subjects. In the beginning, at the point of collision of ideas in the subjects, let it call for filling the gaps in existing stratified knowledge, finding connections between them.

We found it necessary to express integration in education as follows:

1. Forming a holistic image of the whole being is considered here as the goal of integration of education;
2. Finding a common platform to bring different scientific knowledge closer together.
3. As a means of developing education.

4. As a means of universal, national education.

In the establishment of connections between two educational subjects and their integration, one or another subject serves as a basis from time to time. The basis of integrated lessons should be the organic connection and logical interrelationship of topics in different academic subjects.

Integrative Approach in Primary Education

An integrative approach in primary education blends different subjects, teaching methods, and activities to offer a well-rounded learning experience. This approach can enhance creative thinking by:

1. **Merging Disciplines:** Combining subjects like science, art, and literature helps students see connections between different areas of knowledge, encouraging broader and more creative thinking.

- Example: A project that integrates science and art, such as constructing models of the solar system while studying planets, encourages students to use knowledge from both fields creatively.

2. **Employing Project-Based Learning:** This method involves students working on projects that require research, teamwork, and creative problem-solving, allowing them to apply their knowledge in practical ways.

- Example: Designing a sustainable city as a project involves learning from environmental science, engineering, and urban planning, fostering creativity in finding solutions.

3. **Promoting Collaborative Learning:** Group work and discussions enable students to exchange ideas, learn from one another, and develop their creative thinking through collaboration.

- Example: Brainstorming sessions to address community issues help students combine ideas and devise innovative solutions together.

4. **Using Inquiry-Based Learning:** This approach encourages students to ask questions, explore answers, and engage in hands-on activities, nurturing curiosity and critical thinking.

- Example: An inquiry-based unit on ecosystems where students research different habitats and create their own miniature ecosystem promotes exploration and creative problem-solving.

5. **Incorporating Arts and Humanities:** Including arts and humanities in the curriculum allows students to creatively express themselves and explore diverse perspectives.

- Example: Writing and performing a play about historical events helps students learn history through creative expression.

Advantages of the Integrative Approach

- **Increased Engagement:** Combining subjects and methods makes learning more interesting and relevant for students.

- **Enhanced Problem-Solving Skills:** Applying knowledge across different areas improves students' ability to solve problems creatively.

- **Wider Perspectives:** Exposure to various disciplines helps students approach problems from multiple angles, fostering innovation.

- **Greater Motivation:** Creative projects and group activities can boost students' enthusiasm and interest in learning.

Challenges and Considerations

- **Curriculum Design:** Crafting an integrative curriculum requires careful planning to ensure all subjects are effectively covered and learning goals are achieved.

- Teacher Training: Educators need appropriate training and support to implement integrative methods and manage interdisciplinary projects.

- Assessment: Evaluating students' creative thinking and problem-solving skills can be challenging and may require new assessment approaches.

An integrative approach in primary education provides a valuable method for developing children's creative thinking skills. By combining different subjects, teaching strategies, and activities, educators can create an enriching learning environment that promotes creativity, problem-solving, and critical thinking. Despite the challenges, this approach offers significant benefits for nurturing young learners' creativity.

As a result of observing and analyzing the data, we came to the following conclusions. The formation of creative thinking of students is the need of the hour. Primary school teachers have a big role in this process. They need to identify and constantly develop the creative thinking skills of their students, teach them to analyze and compare. Also, they are responsible for encouraging students' creative abilities and creating a friendly atmosphere, making creative thinking a habit. Creativity does not become a habit among students who are afraid of making mistakes, afraid of success, paying attention to excessive grades, and fearing criticism. In the rapidly developing global world, the teacher must be constantly in search, be active in the field of education with new ideas and thoughts. The use of interdisciplinary integration is of particular importance in teaching students to be creative and to be able to freely get out of various situations that they may encounter in life. Although the integrated approach to subjects requires more time from the teacher in the process of preparing lessons, it will show its positive result in the future.

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